

STUDIES ON BASIC SULPHATES OF BIVALENT METALS. PART IV. Be

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Thermometric titrations of beryllium sulphate with sodium hydroxide solution and *vice versa* indicate the existence of the basic sulphate $\text{BeSO}_4 \cdot \text{BeO}$.

Beryllium being a bivalent metal is expected to show similarity with other bivalent metals such as Cu, Zn, Cd, etc. In previous papers (Haldar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 147, 183) it has been shown by the author that Cu, Zn and Cd give basic sulphates of the type $\text{RSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{RO}$ where R = Cu, Zn or Cd in all concentration ranges and the basic salt $\text{RSO}_4 \cdot \text{RO}$ exists only in concentrated solution. However, at the outset it cannot be said with any certainty about the type of basic beryllium sulphate, although it is expected that either of the type $\text{RSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{RO}$ or $\text{RSO}_4 \cdot \text{RO}$ or both of them will be given by beryllium. This is due to the fact that as a bivalent metal only general similarity with other bivalent metals is expected and it being a typical element, may not show similarity with other bivalent metals in detail. Indications of basic salt, hydroxide and beryllate formations are expected to be observed in the temperature-concentration curves and hence the author has titrated beryllium sulphate with caustic soda solution and *vice versa* by thermometric method. That, beryllium hydroxide dissolves in alkali hydroxide solution naturally suggests a beryllate formation which, however, points to its similarity with Cu and Zn and probably with Cd, which has also been reported to give cadmates. But no indication of cadmate formation has been observed by thermometric method, although in the case of Cu and Zn, distinct indications of cuprate and zincate formations are obtained by this method.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The thermometric apparatus is the same as that has been described in a previous paper (Haldar, *loc. cit.*). Reagents used were all of 'Analar' quality. Beryllium was estimated as beryllium oxide.

TABLE I

NaOH solution = 0.4843 M. 40 C. c. of 0.05004 M- BeSO_4 soln. used.

NaOH soln. added.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.	NaOH soln. added.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.	NaOH soln. added.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	2.010	0.000	7 c.c.	1.500	0.510	14 c.c.	1.380	0.630
1	1.920	.090	8	1.450	.560	15	1.370	.640
2	1.830	.180	9	1.430	.580	16	1.370	.640
3	1.740	.270	10	1.420	.590	18	1.350	.660
4	1.660	.350	11	1.410	.600	20	1.330	.680
5	1.610	.400	12	1.400	.610	22	1.310	.700
6	1.550	.460	13	1.390	.620	24	1.290	.720

TABLE II

NaOH solution = 0.9686 M. 40 C. c. of 0.1008 M-BeSO₄ soln. used.

NaOH soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.	NaOH soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.	NaOH soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	2.570	0.000	4 c.c.	1.960	0.610	8 c.c.	1.630	0.940
1	2.390	.180	5	1.860	.710	9	1.610	.960
2	2.240	.330	6	1.780	.790	10	1.610	.960
3	2.100	.470	7	1.700	.870	11	1.610	.960
						12	1.610	.960

TABLE III

BeSO₄ soln. = 0.5040 M. 40 C. c. of 0.1008M-NaOH soln. used.

BeSO ₄ soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.	BeSO ₄ soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.	BeSO ₄ soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	4.520	0.000	4 c.c.	4.100	0.420	8 c.c.	4.065	0.455
1	4.390	.130	5	4.080	.440	9	4.065	.455
2	4.270	.250	6	4.075	.445	10	4.065	.455
3	4.140	.380	7	4.070	.450	11	4.065	.455
						12	4.065	.455

TABLE IV

BeSO₄ soln. = 0.5040 M. 40 C. c. of 0.1262M-NaOH soln. used.

BeSO ₄ soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.	BeSO ₄ soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.	BeSO ₄ soln.	Temp. reading.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	5.050	0.000	6 c.c.	4.250	0.800	12 c.c.	4.060	0.990
1	4.870	.180	7	4.210	.840	13	4.040	1.010
2	4.700	.350	8	4.170	.880	14	4.020	1.030
3	4.530	.520	9	4.130	.920	15	4.000	1.050
4	4.380	.670	10	4.100	.950	16	3.980	1.070
5	4.280	.770	11	4.080	.970	18	3.940	1.110

DISCUSSION

All the temperature-concentration curves show break at the point beryllium sulphate : caustic soda = 1 : 1. This undoubtedly points to the basic salt formation of the type BeSO₄.BeO. But no indication of the basic salt, BeSO₄.3BeO is observed, although it has been observed in the case of Cu, Zn and Cd. Breaks corresponding to normal hydroxide do not appear exactly at the point BeSO₄ : NaOH = 1 : 2, but 1 : 1.92, when BeSO₄ solutions are titrated with caustic soda solutions. This result is in accordance with that of Britton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2122) who observed electrometrically inflexion in the *p_H*-concentration curves when 1.91 equivalent of alkali was added to BeSO₄ solution. In reverse thermometric titrations i.e., when Be sulphate solution is added to caustic soda solution, change in the straight line curves

takes place at the point $\text{BeSO}_4 : \text{NaOH} = 7 : 16$. This change is probably not due to beryllate formation, for, if this would have been the case, it would

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

have been indicated when caustic soda solution was added to BeSO₄ solution. It may be explained as, Be sulphate begins to react with the precipitated Be hydroxide before the precipitation of the hydroxide is complete, to form the stable basic sulphate BeSO₄.BeO. Thus although it has been observed by all that Be hydroxide dissolves in alkali hydroxide, no indication of beryllate formation is obtained from thermometric titration curves. The existence of the basic salt BeSO₄.BeO suggests that hydrolysis of Be sulphate in dilute solution should take place according to the equation

or

... (1)

It has actually been observed that Be sulphate solution is acidic and the hydrolysis in dilute solution takes place according to the above equation. But if one passes from dilute solution to increasingly concentrated solution, it is observed that the behaviour becomes quite different. Dilute solution of Be sulphate can take up 1 mol. of BeO per mol. of Be sulphate in accordance to the above mechanism, but concentrated solution of Be sulphate can take up even two mols. of BeO per mol. of Be sulphate. Again in the case of normal hydrolysis, it is an established fact that hydrolysis increases with dilution. But in concentrated solution of Be sulphate, hydrolysis, as observed from hydrogen ion activity of the solution by Pritz (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, **24**, 281), increases with increasing concentration of the salt. Britton's view of colloidal aggregate formation between $\text{Be}(\text{OH})_2$ and BeSO_4 in concentrated solution cannot be supported by experimental evidences, although he, as support to his views, has referred to the observation of Parsons, Robinson and Fuller (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1907, **11**, 651). It was observed by them that the freezing point of BeSO_4 solution was slightly raised by the addition of the oxide and its conductivity slightly diminished. But it is to be noted that they themselves conclude that the basic solutions are not colloidal, since they cannot be separated by dialysis and are not coagulated by electrolysis. They suggested to explain the oxide dissolving in the salt as camphor dissolves in acetic acid even when it is diluted with water. Sidgewick and Lewis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1287) are, however, of opinion that the oxide combines with the beryllium ion to form a complex cation $[\text{Be}(4 \text{ BeO})]^{++}$. But this view too presents certain difficulties. If the beryllated ion be of the form as stated above, then it suggests that one mol. of BeSO_4 will dissolve 4 mols of BeO, which is not the case. Secondly, with the above view it is too difficult to explain the high acidity of concentrated BeSO_4 solution. From the solubility measurements Punche and Josien (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1940, **7**, 755, 955) have concluded that the basic sulphate $\text{BeSO}_4 \cdot \text{BeO}$ exists only. They have tried to explain the high solubility of beryllium oxide in beryllium sulphate as due to colloidal aggregate formation, although they have not been able to discard the observations of Parsons, Robinson and Fuller (*loc. cit.*). So it is clear that normal hydrolysis of BeSO_4 takes place only in dilute solutions and after a certain concentration, a new type of reaction mechanism takes place. Considering the high acidity of concentrated BeSO_4 solution it is probable that a complex acid of the type $\text{H}_n \left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{OH})_n \\ \text{Be} \\ \text{SO}_4 \end{array} \right]$ exists in the solution and with dilution this passes over to the basic salt $(\text{BeOH})_2\text{SO}_4$ and then the normal hydrolysis proceeds. The nature of the complex acid is, however, to be determined and further investigation is needed for it.

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